

KEY CONCEPTS IN BUILDING FIRST AID SKILLS IN STUDENTS: A THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE

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The article examines current approaches to first aid training, highlighting key issues in educational programs, such as inadequate theoretical knowledge, a lack of practical training sessions, and low student motivation. The need to incorporate innovative methods, including simulation training, interactive multimedia tools, and role-playing exercises, is emphasized to enhance the effectiveness of the training process. The authors stress the importance of fostering a culture of first aid as a critical element of public safety and social responsibility. The article concludes with recommendations for a comprehensive overhaul of training programs, focusing on achieving a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical experience.

INTRODUCTION. Modern approaches to first aid training are focused not only on the transfer of theoretical knowledge, but also on the development of practical skills that allow students to act confidently under stress. However, the existing training system in non-medical universities is characterized by a number of problems: insufficient hours allocated to studying first aid, a shortage of qualified teachers, weak student motivation and limited use of modern educational technologies [3]. Many programs are focused primarily on the theoretical aspect, which leads to low training efficiency, since without practical training, students feel unsure when providing assistance in real life [4].

Another problem is the lack of a comprehensive approach to first aid training. Including basic courses in university programs is an important step, but their content is often limited to general information, which does not allow students to fully master the algorithms for providing assistance. In addition, first aid teaching in most cases is not accompanied by

mandatory practical exams, which reduces the level of students' training and their readiness to act in extreme conditions [5].

In view of the above, it is necessary to revise educational approaches, including strengthening practical training, integrating interactive methods, using simulation training and role-playing scenarios. Such technologies allow trainees not only to memorize algorithms for providing assistance, but also to develop confidence in their actions, reducing the level of anxiety in emergency situations [2; pp. 184-192].

The aim of the study is to conduct a theoretical analysis of existing approaches to teaching first aid to students of non-medical universities and to identify key problems in this area. The following tasks were set within the framework of the work: to analyze the theoretical foundations of first aid and its importance in the education system; to study the existing methods of teaching first aid skills in non-medical universities; to identify the main problems associated with the deficiencies in theoretical and practical training of students; to justify the need to introduce innovative teaching methods aimed at improving the effectiveness of preparing students to provide first aid. The object of the study is the process of developing first aid skills in students of non-medical universities, and the subject is modern educational approaches to teaching first aid, their effectiveness and prospects for improvement. The scientific novelty of the work lies in a comprehensive analysis of the existing first aid training system and proposing effective methods for its improvement with an emphasis on practical training and the use of modern teaching technologies. Thus, consideration of this topic is relevant and in demand in light of the need to improve the level of public safety and the readiness of citizens to provide emergency care in critical situations.

The study uses data on the historical evolution of first aid, from the activities of medieval monastic orders to modern educational standards, including the use of simulation technologies and interactive teaching methods [6]. The main protocols for providing assistance, such as BLS (basic life support) and CPR (cardiopulmonary resuscitation), as well as their adaptation in educational programs for students of non-medical specialties are considered [7].

The existing educational systems in higher education institutions were analyzed, key problems were identified, including a lack of theoretical training, a limited number of practical classes and a low level of student motivation [8]. The impact of the shortage of academic hours allocated to mastering first aid on the level of training of students was assessed [2; pp. 184-192]. The methodology of teaching first aid was also studied, taking into account the use of modern educational technologies, such as virtual reality, multimedia

simulators and role-playing scenarios, ensuring more effective acquisition of theoretical knowledge and development of practical skills [4].

In addition, an analysis of regulatory documents governing the teaching of first aid in universities of Uzbekistan was conducted, with an emphasis on the integration of relevant courses into educational programs. Changes made to the curricula since 2000, including the introduction of disciplines related to health protection, as well as their practical application in the training of students were considered [5].

Particular attention is paid to assessing students' motivation for learning first aid. The studies indicate a low level of awareness of the importance of this knowledge among students of non-medical universities, which is due to the lack of integration of the topic into the main disciplines and the lack of practical classes [10]. Methods for increasing motivation are considered, including the introduction of practical exams, participation in volunteer programs and the use of real cases demonstrating the importance of timely assistance [3].

Historical analysis has shown that first aid as a structured discipline began to develop in the second half of the 19th century, but its integration into the educational programs of non-medical universities has not yet reached the required level. In modern conditions, the emphasis in first aid training is shifting towards interactive and simulation methods, but their implementation in the educational process remains insufficient [2, pp. 184–192]. In this regard, students experience a deficit of practical skills, which affects their confidence in their own actions in real emergency situations [3].

An analysis of educational programs of non-medical universities of the Republic of Uzbekistan showed that the discipline "Fundamentals of Medical Knowledge" occupies only an insignificant place in the structure of students' training. For example, within the framework of the correspondence form of study in the direction of "Primary Education" at the Urgench State University, 120 hours are allocated for this course, of which only 24 are allocated for classroom studies, and 96 hours are allocated for independent work [2, pp. 184-192]. This leads to the fact that most students do not receive a sufficient number of practical classes necessary for developing automaticity of actions under stress.

One of the main reasons for the low level of training is the insufficient connection between the theoretical and practical aspects of training. Even with basic theoretical knowledge, students face difficulties in applying it in practice, which indicates the need to develop new teaching methods [4]. The introduction of modern technologies such as virtual

reality (VR), interactive multimedia courses and simulators contributes to more effective assimilation of material, but their use remains fragmented [2, pp. 184–192].

In addition, a low level of student motivation to study first aid has been identified, which is due to the insufficient integration of this topic into general educational programs. A study conducted at one of the universities in Taif (Saudi Arabia) found that only 14% of students in non-medical specialties receive adequate training in first aid, which confirms the existing gaps in the educational system [10]. Similar results were obtained at Yarmouk University (Jordan), where a shortage of both theoretical and practical classes in first aid was noted, which reduces the level of students' readiness to act in extreme situations [11].

Problems in the organization of the educational process related to the lack of a comprehensive approach to the formation of a first aid culture have also been identified. According to the World Health Organization, up to 60% of fatal cases could be prevented if the people around had basic skills in providing emergency aid [1]. However, current educational programs do not provide the required level of training, as they are limited to studying general safety issues and do not provide for in-depth mastery of algorithms for actions in critical situations [5].

Thus, the analysis showed that the effectiveness of first aid training in non-medical universities remains low due to insufficient theoretical training, lack of practical classes, weak student motivation and lack of integration of modern educational technologies. To improve the situation, it is necessary to revise the curricula with an increase in hours for practical training, introduce innovative teaching methods such as simulation training and role-playing scenarios, and develop new methodological approaches aimed at increasing students' awareness and responsibility.

References:

1. Палванова, У. Б., & Тургунов, С. Т. (2024, August). Обобщение научного исследования по совершенствованию навыков оказания первой помощи студентов не медицинских высших учебных заведений. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE* (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 16-17).
2. Палванова, У. Б., & Тургунов, С. Т. (2024, August). Обобщение научного исследования по совершенствованию навыков оказания первой помощи студентов не медицинских высших учебных заведений. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE* (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 16-17).
3. Палванова, У., Тургунов, С., & Якубова, А. (2024). АНАЛИЗ ПРОЦЕССОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ НАВЫКАМ ОКАЗАНИЯ ПЕРВОЙ ПОМОЩИ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕ

МЕДИЦИНСКИХ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ. *Journal of universal science research*, 2(7), 85-94.

4. Палванова, У. Б. (2024). Значение Формирования Навыков Оказания Первой Помощи У Студентов В Не Медицинских Образовательных Учреждениях. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 27, 93-98.

5. Палванова, У. Б. (2024). Значение Формирования Навыков Оказания Первой Помощи У Студентов В Не Медицинских Образовательных Учреждениях. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 27, 93-98.

6. Палванова, У. Б., & Тургунов, С. Т. (2024, August). Обобщение научного исследования по совершенствованию навыков оказания первой помощи студентам не медицинских высших учебных заведений. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE* (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 16-17).

7. Палванова, У., Якубова, А., & Юсупова, Ш. (2023). УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРИ СПЛЕНОМЕГАЛИИ. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(21).

8. Палванова, У. Б., Изранов, В. А., Гордова, В. С., & Якубова, А. Б. (2021). Спленомегалия по УЗИ—есть ли универсальные критерии?. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 2(3), 52-27.

9. Степанян, И. А., Изранов, В. А., Гордова, В. С., Белецкая, М. А., & Палванова, У. Б. (2021). Ультразвуковое исследование печени: поиск наиболее воспроизводимой и удобной в применении методики измерения косого краниокаудального размера правой доли. *Лучевая диагностика и терапия*, 11(4), 68-79.

10. Палванова, У. Б. (2024). Значение Формирования Навыков Оказания Первой Помощи У Студентов В Не Медицинских Образовательных Учреждениях. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 27, 93-98.

11. Якубова, А. Б., Палванова, У. Б., & Палванова, С. Б. (2018). НОВЕЙШИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ СТУДЕНТОВ МЕДИЦИНСКОГО КОЛЛЕДЖА В ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. In *Современные медицинские исследования* (pp. 22-25).

12. Изранов, В. А., Степанян, И. А., Гордова, В. С., & Палванова, У. Б. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОГО ДОСТУПА И ГЛУБИНЫ ДЫХАНИЯ НА КОСОЙ ВЕРТИКАЛЬНЫЙ РАЗМЕР ПРАВОЙ ДОЛИ ПЕЧЕНИ. In *РАДИОЛОГИЯ–2020* (pp. 24-24).

13. Якубова, А. Б., & Палванова, У. Б. Проблемы здоровья связанные с экологией среди населения Приаралья мақола Научно-медицинский журнал “Авиценна” Выпуск № 13. *Кемерово 2017г*, 12-15.

14. Азада, Б. Я., & Умида, Б. П. (2017). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЗДОРОВЬЯ СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ЭКОЛОГИЕЙ СРЕДИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ПРАРАЛЬЯ. *Авиценна*, (13), 12-14.

15. Izranov, V., Palvanova, U., Gordova, V., Perepelitsa, S., & Morozov, S. (2019). Ultrasound criteria of splenomegaly. *The Radiologist*, 1(1002), 3-6.

16. Batirovna, Y. A., Bahramovna, P. U., Bahramovna, P. S., & Ogli, I. A. U. (2019). Effective treatment of patients with chronic hepatitis, who live in ecologically unfavorable South zone of Aral Sea region. *Наука, образование и культура*, (2 (36)), 50-52.

17. Stepanyan, I. A., Izranov, V. A., Gordova, V. S., Palvanova, U., & Stepanyan, S. A. (2020). The influence of diffuse liver diseases on the size and spleen mass coefficient, prognostic value of indicators. *Virchows Archiv-European Journal of Pathology*, 477(S1), 279-279.

18. Изранов, В. А., Степанян, И. А., Гордова, В. С., & Палванова, У. Б. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОГО ДОСТУПА И ГЛУБИНЫ ДЫХАНИЯ НА КОСОЙ ВЕРТИКАЛЬНЫЙ РАЗМЕР ПРАВОЙ ДОЛИ ПЕЧЕНИ. In *РАДИОЛОГИЯ–2020* (pp. 24-24).

19. Изранов, В. А., Степанян, И. А., Гордова, В. С., & Палванова, У. Б. (2020). ВЛИЯНИЕ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВОГО ДОСТУПА И ГЛУБИНЫ ДЫХАНИЯ НА КОСОЙ ВЕРТИКАЛЬНЫЙ РАЗМЕР ПРАВОЙ ДОЛИ ПЕЧЕНИ. In *РАДИОЛОГИЯ–2020* (pp. 24-24).

20. Stepanyan, I. A., Izranov, V. A., Gordova, V. S., Palvanova, U., & Stepanyan, S. A. (2020). Correlation of pathological changes in the liver and spleen in patients with cirrhosis. *Virchows Archiv-European Journal of Pathology*, 477(S1), 278-279.

21. Stepanyan, I. A., Izranov, V. A., Gordova, V. S., Palvanova, U., & Stepanyan, S. A. (2020). The influence of diffuse liver diseases on the size and spleen mass coefficient, prognostic value of indicators. *Virchows Archiv-European Journal of Pathology*, 477(S1), 279-279.

22. Stepanyan, I. A., Izranov, V. A., Gordova, V. S., & Stepanyan, S. A. (2020). Diagnostic significance of liver stiffness and the sizes of the caudate and left lobes with viral hepatitis and cirrhosis. *Virchows Archiv-European Journal of Pathology*, 477(S1), 279-279.

23. Stepanyan, I. A., Izranov, V. A., Gordova, V. S., Beleckaya, M. A., & Palvanova, U. B. (2021). Ultrasound examination of the liver: the search for the most reproducible and easy to operate measuring method of the right lobe oblique craniocaudal diameter. *Diagnostic radiology and radiotherapy*, 11(4), 68-79.

24. Степанян, И. А., Изранов, В. А., Гордова, В. С., Белецкая, М. А., & Палванова, У. Б. (2021). Ультразвуковое исследование печени: поиск наиболее воспроизводимой и удобной в применении методики измерения косого краниокаудального размера правой доли. *Лучевая диагностика и терапия*, 11(4), 68-79.